

Collecting DMP Requirements for NFDI

Report on DMP4NFDI activities

DMP4NFDI is the basic service in development for data management planning within NFDI. The service supports NFDI consortia providing services for data management plans (DMPs), software management plans (SMPs) or analog concepts. It offers RDMO hosting, support & training for consortia staff and develops and maintains the NFDI DMP Template Framework to facilitate template development and interoperability, and it supports consortia to integrate DMPs, SMPs etc. with their service portfolio.

During the initial development phase (June 2024 - May 2025), we are collecting requirements for DMP and SMP services¹ in the NFDI by organizing workshops and exchanges with the consortia and the general RDM community. This report summarizes our results after three workshops, participation in two hackathons, presenting the service at several occasions and exchange with consortia in infra-dmp and individual meetings. We thank all who participated in our events and discussions and provided feedback. In particular, we thank those consortia that committed to act as use cases during the initialization phase: NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Earth, and NFDI4Memory.

Service concept

Our service is based on previous work by infra-dmp, the NFDI working group on data management planning of the NFDI section Common Infrastructures.² Here, the participating consortia exchanged visions for DMPs, discussed quality criteria for DMP templates and DMP tools used or planned to be used for DMP services in the NFDI.³ In a survey across all NFDI consortia, we collected information on staff members responsible for DMPs in the consortia, DMP tools, template development and planned training activities. The initial survey was initiated in 2022, but remained to be open for updates. Until now, 23 consortia provided information. 14 consortia mentioned RDMO⁴ as their DMP tool of choice, one consortium developed its own solution, while the others have been undecided. 12 consortia mentioned planned template development and 11 training activities.

Infra-dmp organized workshops on “Best practices in template development” and “What can DMPs achieve?” in 2023, and another workshop on “Quality criteria for DMP templates” in 2024. A general vision for DMPs in the NFDI was broadly discussed and developed together, and eventually published as the white paper “A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI”.⁵ This paper states a general need for standardization of DMP templates across NFDI

¹ This also includes analog concepts sometimes summarized as “Output Management Plan”, e.g. in the DataCite schema, DataCite Metadata Working Group (2024)

² Enke et al. (2023)

³ Diederichs et al. (2024a); Krause et al (2024)

⁴ Research Data Management Organiser: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>

⁵ Diederichs et al. (2024a)

in order to achieve and implement the machine-actionable DMP⁶, i.e. connected and integrated DMP services across NFDI.

Based on this work, we developed the initial concept for the DMP4NFDI basic service which provides support for the consortia on three levels: 1) RDMO hosting and integration, 2) DMP template standardization, 3) Support and training.⁷ The concept is further discussed and developed during the initialization phase of the basic service in order to provide a general service which supports all consortia in offering DMP and SMP services for their respective communities.

DMP Template development

During the first months of the service development, we supported a use case from NFDI4Earth in the development of an RDMO template for the earth system sciences, which was presented and discussed in our first workshop on September 30th 2024 together with a first draft of the NFDI DMP Template Framework. This framework is meant to support consortia in developing a community-specific template, but still ensures interoperability across the NFDI through standardization of generic aspects and usage of the internal RDMO DMP vocabulary.⁸ For testing during the workshop, DMP4NFDI hosted a demo instance with this template and other frequently used templates, in RDMO referred to as “catalogs”, and all participants were assigned as editors to get access to the management interface to discuss catalog development in RDMO.

Following a hands-on session in which the challenges of creating templates with RDMO were discussed, a general need for support in catalog development, especially for the identification of attributes of the internal RDMO vocabulary, was expressed. The consortia expect to have high initial costs, as training is time-consuming and achieving interoperability a complex task, while at the same time they assume that once catalogs are in place, updates require less effort. From this we conclude that instead of investing much time in intensively training consortia staff, it seems that offering a service that heavily supports the initial set-up of catalogs, combined with fundamental training that is sufficient for basic use and updating existing catalogs, and conveying didactic methods for effective knowledge transfer, better fulfill the needs of the consortia. The participants asked for guidance documents, best practices and general support in case they need to update the templates or add more complex content. Taking up this point, we took part in an RDMO hackathon, organized by the LMU Munich on Oct. 16-17th 2024 and worked together with other members of the RDMO community to renew the tutorial for catalog development, the results of which are soon to be made available.⁹

For our second workshop, we invited all members of the infra-dmp working group. As there were very different levels of experience with the RDMO tool, complete beginners and advanced editors, we decided to divide the participants into two groups, one to start with RDMO basics, the other to dive deeper into the NFDI DMP Template Framework. We again

⁶ Bakos, Miksa, Rauber (2018)

⁷ Diederichs et al (2024b)

⁸ See RDMO domain in the RDMO Github repository: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master-rdmo2.x/rdmorganiser/domain>

⁹ More information on the hackathon at https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/RDMO_Hackathon_2024

gathered feedback on the general RDMO usage, the template framework and needs and wishes for the DMP4NFDI services. For beginners, the user interface and different elements available in RDMO seemed overwhelming at the beginning, and the need for step-by-step guidance was expressed by the group, e.g. in the form of videos. In addition, a contact point which supports catalog development was requested. The experienced participants in the second group had already worked as editors in RDMO and were able to easily adapt the idea of the template framework. The catalog provided was very comprehensive and helpful, and it was discussed which questions should build a basis for the framework.

In general, providing support and offering training material and guidance for the template development was requested, which is in line with our current service concept. The idea of the NFDI DMP Template Framework was well received, but there is still a need to discuss general aspects of DMP templates across NFDI. On the other hand, the consortia requested more support in template development than we initially expected. Further, they would like to get support in planning outreach activities to involve their community and raise awareness of DMPs and SMPs. We will address these issues in the following integration phase of the service by providing additional resources for template development and include support for outreach measures.

RDMO hosting and integration

For the DMP4NFDI basic service, a multitenant RDMO instance is used to host RDMO clients for the NFDI consortia. All clients share a single database to allow template exchange and cross-consortia DMPs. RDMO has been chosen because of the wide support of the NFDI consortia, the multitenant functionality which allows collaboration across the consortia, and the RDMO community, which has been actively developing templates for years, also for discipline-specific requirements.¹⁰ Recently, around 20 institutions founded the RDMO association committing to the sustainability of the open source software tool.¹¹ For service integration, RDMO provides an API and plugin architecture, which already has been used to connect RDMO DMPs and SMPs to other services.¹²

During our workshops and meetings, several requirements concerning RDMO have been raised by the consortia.

User interface

- A general comment concerns the RDMO user interface which needs to become more intuitive in order to better guide the users. A task fortunately already tackled by the RDMO community.¹³

Catalog development

- Improved search across elements: The search for catalog elements allows searching for titles, but not for content or keywords. For catalog development, an improved search across the existing elements would highly support the reuse of existing

¹⁰ See RDMO Github for existing templates: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog>

¹¹ RDMO (2025)

¹² Windeck et al. (2024); Castro et al. (2023)

¹³ Windeck (2024)

elements. In the past, a search tool has been provided as an own website¹⁴, but the search capabilities are limited.

- Easier selection of attributes: RDMO attributes mediate between all elements in RDMO and thus represent a basic vocabulary that ensures interoperability between templates. But choosing the right attribute for a specific question is a challenge, since only a few attributes are clearly defined. Catalog editors need more support, e.g. by an improved search across attributes and related questions.

Interview section

Some feature requests concern the interview section in RDMO. Some of those have already been proposed as feature requests in the RDMO Github or are in development.

- Offering users to copy information on datasets: At the moment users need to copy information manually between datasets. This feature will be available in the upcoming RDMO release.
- Creating more complex interactive interviews by improving the condition feature: Conditions are targeted at one attribute only and can be combined via OR function, but more complex conditions are needed, e.g. to automate reviews.
- Offering autofill functionality for personal information provided via ORCID integration: Involved personnel and roles are defined in a data management plan, but the information on the person needs to be added manually. ORCID is one database from which some information could be collected automatically.
- The integration of terminology services: Each discipline has specific vocabularies. Reusing terminology services for editors or users could improve understandability and interoperability. At the moment, no support for terminology services is available.

Management and support of users

Other features concern the management and support of users, e.g.

- Improved role and rights management: at the moment user rights have to be assigned by the instance administrators. For some consortia scenarios, specific roles need to be defined, also assigning editor or manager rights should be possible by the consortia themselves in order for the service to scale.
- Validation checks: The information that users store in the DMP should automatically be validated, e.g. when numbers or dates are required. A feature that was just released with the new 2.2.0 version of RDMO.
- Statistics on usage: At the moment there is some information on the number of projects or catalogs used available, but scattered across the interface and there is no time series available. A server script is available to collect statistics, but there is no page in RDMO that visualizes those statistics. For easier monitoring, a feature to visualize and collect usage statistics should be added.

Plugins

- Allow DMP publication: Although there is a Zenodo plugin for RDMO, this does not allow publishing the DMP itself. A plugin was requested to manage this publication via RDMO. This plugin is already being developed by a collaboration between DMP4NFDI and NFDI4Biodiversity.

¹⁴ see <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/>

- Plugin management for clients: Since plugins will play a major role for connecting RDMO to other services, the need for a more sophisticated plugin management also became apparent. At the moment plugins need to be registered via server configurations. If more plugins are used, the consortia members themselves should be able to define plugins and settings via the RDMO interface.

Interoperability with other DMP tools is a major issue, not only concerning the RDMO software, but also the template framework. For years, RDMO supports import and export of information according to the DMP common standard for machine-actionable data management plans (maDMP), developed by an RDA working group and implemented by several tools.¹⁵ This application profile also builds the foundation for the template framework, which will ensure interoperability across the EOSC. In a recent hackathon, organized by NFDI4Datascience, several consortia and the two basic services DMP4NFDI and PID4NFDI discussed the maDMP standard and different mappings. The results are now part of our contribution to the announced update of the maDMP standard by the RDA.¹⁶

Summary and next steps

Collecting requirements in order to improve the DMP4NFDI service is a never-ending task. Still it became apparent that consortia have many similar needs that we can address with our basic service. We will continue collecting feedback and improving our service, e.g. a further workshop is planned for March 2025 at the E-Science Tage in Heidelberg.

For the next phase of the service, we already made a few adjustments, concerning the amount of resources available to support template development and training needed by the consortia, including the support for outreach activities. We will also add a specific focus on software management plans, since those have been neglected in the overall discussion in NFDI, which became apparent during an infra-dmp meeting in May 2024. We will continue to present our work and collect feedback from the consortia and the overall RDM community in order to iteratively improve the DMP4NFDI service and we would like to thank all who have already provided comments and ideas.

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¹⁵ Miksa, Walk, Neish (2020)

¹⁶ RDA DMP Common Standards WG (2024)

References

- Bakos, A., Miksa, T., Rauber, A. (2018). Research Data Preservation Using Process Engines and Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans. In: Méndez, E., Crestani, F., Ribeiro, C., David, G., Lopes, J. (eds) Digital Libraries for Open Knowledge. TPDL 2018. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 11057. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00066-0_6
- Castro, L. J., Geist, L., Gonzalez, E., Gonzalez-Ocanto, M., Grossmann, Y. V., Pronk, T., Solanki, D., Utrilla Guerrero, C., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2023). Five Minutes to Write a Software Management Plan – A Machine-actionable Approach to Simplify the Creation of SMPs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10374839>
- DataCite Metadata Working Group (2024). DataCite Metadata Schema for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.6. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/csba-e454>
- Diederichs, K., Krause, C., Lemaire, M., Reidelbach, M., & Windeck, J. (2024a). A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570654>
- Diederichs, K., Förstner, K., Hausen, D., Jagusch, G., Johannsen, J., Lindstädt, B., Schmitz, D., Schönau, S., Stäcker, T., & Windeck, J. (2024b). DMP4NFDI - NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans (1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13445355>
- Enke, H., Hausen, D., Henzen, C., Jagusch, G., Krause, C., Schönau, S., Weimer, L., & Windeck, J. (2023). Data management planning: Concept for Setting up a Working Group in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructures (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7540682>
- Krause, C., Bergmann, K., Hausen, D. A., Riedel, R., & Windeck, J. (2024). Quality Criteria for DMP Templates (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13347687>
- Miksa, T., Walk, P., & Neish, P. (2020). RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>
- RDA DMP Common Standards WG (2024). DMP Common Standard for maDMPs Maintenance. Blog post on Nov. 28, 2024. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg/posts/?post=171294>
- RDMO (2025): Gründungsversammlung des RDMO-Vereins. https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/Gr%C3%BCndungsversammlung_des_RDMO-Vereins
- Windeck, J. (2024). RDMO UI/UX. RDMO Community Meeting 2024-10-08. https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/12_Community-Treffen
- Windeck, J., Schröder, M., Frenzel, J., Kusmierz, S., Fuchs, H., & Klar, J. (2024). Connecting RDM Services: Interoperability and Interfaces for RDMO. Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement, (2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2024.2.8629>